

Development of efficient and cleaner charcoal stoves for cooking applications in a rural residential dwelling

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Abstract

In the Philippines, nearly 30% of households use charcoal for cooking applications, especially in rural areas. This method of cooking produces contaminants which negatively affects the indoor air quality (IAQ) of the said households. Three (3) charcoal-fuelled cookstoves were designed and fabricated, adapting existing improved cookstove designs. Various parameters were measured to compare the three improved cookstoves and a typical, low-cost cookstove available in the market. Several variables were measured during the performance of a water boiling test in a laboratory set-up. Concentration of identified tracer contaminants, namely CO₂, CO and both inhalable and respirable PM, produced from fuel combustion were assessed. The performance of all four (4) stoves was also compared. All of the improved cookstoves required less time to boil the water, had lower specific fuel consumption, higher thermal efficiency and better turn-down ratio than the typical cookstove. It was also observed that the improved cookstoves produced less of the tracer contaminants than the typical stove.

Keywords

Charcoal cookstoves, indoor air quality, household air pollution

1 Introduction

Biomass fuels such as wood, charcoal or dung are used by more than 2 billion people around the world for cooking and heating purposes due to their cost and availability (MIT 2013). In the Philippines, nearly 30 percent of the energy used comes from biomass fuels and most of this energy is consumed by people in rural areas for household cooking (Samson et al. 2013). The air contaminants produced by these biomass cooking fuels can affect the indoor air quality (IAQ) in residential houses.

Acceptable IAQ refers to the air that does not contain known pollutants and harmful or higher level of concentrations as determined by authorized organizations (ASHRAE 2013). Using solid fuel such as charcoal for cooking indoors can affect the IAQ, which can cause severe health issues. Illnesses like pneumonia, pulmonary disease and lung cancer, which are caused by indoor air pollution due to the use of solid fuel, result in almost two million deaths annually worldwide (WHO 2013).

Pennise et al. (2009) noted that burning of biomass fuels inefficiently produces higher concentrations of contaminants such as carbon monoxide (CO) and fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}). By designing improved cookstoves that will burn biomass fuel efficiently, IAQ in households which use them can be significantly improved—and thus may potentially lessen the health impact of cooking activities in rural areas.

2 Methodology

2.1 Walkthrough

A walkthrough was conducted in a rural residential dwelling in Barangay Molino 2 Bacoor City, Cavite on June 01, 2014 in order to help identify tracer contaminants to be monitored for the study. Tracer contaminants are those pollutants found in indoor air, which are produced by burning charcoal for cooking, and are relatively practical to measure. The walkthrough was conducted on four (4) rural houses to observe the usual

set-up and dimensions of kitchens in the households and to know the typical charcoal-fuelled cookstove used by the residents. The selection of the location for the walkthrough was based on the study by Buere et al. (2014).

2.2 Design and fabrication of improved cookstoves

Three existing designs of improved cookstove were modified and adapted for the study. The existing stove designs were the following: Philippine QB stove (S1), burn stove and Kool Kalan (S3). The materials for the stoves were chosen based on thermal properties and structural integrity. Heat transfer was the main consideration for design calculations. Computer modeling was not used during the design process.

The modified designs were sketched using AutoCAD to serve as a guide during the fabrication. Stainless steel was used as the main material for the improved stoves' structure. The metal parts of the stoves such as the firebox, ashtray, grate and outer were fabricated in a machine shop. For the clay firebox of the modified Kool Kalan, a thinner clay pot with similar dimensions to the original design was purchased due to unavailability of a contractor which could fabricate a clay firebox with the exact dimensions designed. For the insulation of the modified Philippine QB Stove and the modified burn cookstove, powdered perlite was mixed with water and a small amount cement. The perlite mixture was poured into the metal shell and was left to dry. Figure 1 shows the developed stoves and the typical stove used in the study. The "typical stove" (S4) used in the study was the stove commonly used in the area included in the walkthrough and was purchased from the local market within the vicinity.

2.3 Experimental set-up

2.3.1 IAQ assessment equipment

Carbon dioxide (CO₂) concentration was measured using a direct reading passive sampler (brand: Telaire 7001). CO was assessed using colorimetric tubes and its recommended handheld piston pump (brand: RAE Systems, Inc.). Inhalable (PM_i) and respirable (PM_r) particulate matter (PM) were collected using an IOM personal sampler (brand: SKC, Inc). PM sampling filters and assembly used were the following: 25 mm, 0.8 um MCE filter; MultiDust Foam Discs for respirable sampling; and Cassette Assembly for IOM Sampler in conductive plastic. Instructions from the supplier product manuals were observed prior to sampling.

Figure 1 – The different stoves used in the study:
(a) S1- Modified Philippine QB stove, (b) S2- Modified burn cookstove,
(c) S3- Modified Kool-Kalan, and (d) S4- Typical stove

2.3.2 Laboratory set-up

The experiment was conducted inside the IAQ laboratory at the Mapua Institute of Technology. The laboratory set-up was based on field observations of actual kitchens during the walkthrough. For each test run, each stove was placed on a table located 700 mm from the window, which served as the primary means to exhaust the combustion gases. The equipment used for IAQ assessment was placed at the breathing zone level on top of a platform with a height of 1510 mm, beside the cookstove assembly. The equipment placement was intended to mimic actual conditions experienced at the breathing zone by an occupant using a cookstove. The window opening was kept constant to 410 mm X 1470 mm for the whole duration of the tests. The floor-to-ceiling height was 3000 mm. Figure 2 shows the dimensions and placement of equipment during the experiment (not drawn to scale).

Figure 2 – Distances, dimensions and placement of equipment inside the laboratory

2.4 Water boiling test

The procedures used for the stove test were based on the water boiling test (WBT) version 4.2.3 (Global Alliance for Clean Cookstoves 2014). The WBT consists of three phases namely the cold start, the hot start and the simmering phase. In the cold start phase, 2.5 liters of water was boiled in the stove where initially the stove temperature is equal to the room temperature. In the hot start phase, the same volume from a fresh batch of water at room temperature was boiled while the stove was still hot. In the last phase, the remaining water from the hot start phase was simmered for 45 minutes. At the beginning of each phase, the water temperature, initial weight of pot with water, initial weight of charcoal and starting time were measured. Likewise, measurements taken after each phase were the final water temperature, weight of pot with remaining water, final weight of charcoal, weight of ash and time to boil. The moisture content of the charcoal used was also determined, as part of the WBT. An excel spreadsheet available from the Global Alliance for Clean Cookstoves was used to calculate the results of the test.

2.5 Assessment and evaluation of contaminants

The concentration of contaminants and measurement of IAQ parameters were measured by following an IAQ protocol during each of the WBT phases. Background concentrations were measured before the start of the test for each stove. Inside CO₂ concentration was measured every five minutes, while outside concentration was recorded every 15 minutes. The measurement of CO was done after each water boiling test phase, and followed the sampling protocol recommended by the manufacturer of the colorimetric tubes. The time for CO and PM sampling were not constant for all tests due to the variability of the time for the cold hot start testing phases for each stove. The PM collection duration was varied—which commonly took less than 30 minutes. The recommended maximum sampling time according is 30 minutes. The MDHS 14/4 of the Health and Safety Executive and the user manual of the equipment supplier was used as bases for the PM sampling protocol.

Table 1 shows the limits used to evaluate the indoor contaminants measured. For CO₂ and PM, the limits set by the American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists (ACGIH) was used. CO₂ and CO limits were time-weighted averages (TWA). Consequently, the World Health Organization (WHO) limit was used for CO concentration evaluation. The reference for these standards was ASHRAE standard 62.1-2010.

Table 1 Limits used to evaluate the indoor air quality parameters

Parameters	Standard Values	Duration	Basis
CO ₂	5000 ppm	8-h TWA	ACGIH
CO	90 ppm	15-min TWA	WHO
PM _i	10,000 µg/m ³	Ceiling	ACGIH
PM _r	3,000 µg/m ³	Ceiling	ACGIH

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Indoor air quality

3.1.1 Carbon dioxide

Table 2 shows the mean CO₂ concentrations at the breathing zone for each of the WBT phases of each stove. For the background concentration measurement, the improved stove 1 had the highest CO₂ concentration, while the other stoves had background concentrations which were very similar to each other. S3 had the lowest 8-h TWA CO₂ concentration, followed by S2. The traditional stove had the highest 8-h TWA CO₂ concentration followed by the improved stove 1. The average CO₂ concentrations outdoors for each of the stoves were nearly of the same values throughout the tests conducted. The TWA of CO₂ concentrations obtained for each stove were within the ACGIH limit.

Table 2 Average CO₂ concentrations in the breathing zone for each stove during the different WBT phases

WBT Phase	S1, ppm	S2, ppm	S3, ppm	S4, ppm
Background	912	634	614	659
Cold Start	1,707	1,309	1,390	1,690
Hot Start	1,731	1,129	1,271	1,684
Simmering	1,686	652	675	1,187
8hr-TWA	716	551	516	761

3.1.2 Carbon monoxide

Table 3 shows the CO concentration obtained for each of the stoves during the WBT phases. No CO concentration were detected during the background concentration measurements. For all the WBT phases, S2 had the lowest CO concentrations, while S1 had the highest concentrations for most WBT phases. Values typed in bold in table 3 are the CO concentrations which went beyond the referenced limit concentration. Only the improved stove 2 had CO concentrations which were within the limit for all the WBT phases.

Table 3 Levels of CO for each stove during the different WBT phases

WBT Phase	S1, ppm	S2, ppm	S3, ppm	S4, ppm
Background	0	0	0	0
Cold Start	160	80	> 200	196
Hot Start	>200	70	164	124
Simmering (15-min)	170	13	30	140
Simmering (45-min)	90	0	13	46

3.1.3 Particulate matter

Tables 4 and 5, respectively, show the amount of PM_i and PM_r for each of the stoves and the WBT phases. For the PM_i, S4 had the lowest average concentration followed by S3. For PM_r, S3 had the lowest average concentration followed by S4. Considering background concentrations, S4 had the lowest concentrations for both PM_i and PM_r, followed by S3.

From the results, the background concentrations of PM_i were within the ACGIH limit. The concentrations of PM_i for the cold and hot start phases for all the stoves exceed the reference limit. For the simmering phase, all the PM_i concentrations except for S1 were within the reference limit.

For the PM_r, the background concentrations (except for S4) were within the reference limit. The PM_r concentrations for the cold start phase for all the stoves were beyond the reference limit. For the hot start phase, only the concentration of S3 fell within the limit. For the simmer phase, the concentrations of S4 and S3 were within the reference limit. The values typed in bold in tables 4 and 5 are the PM concentrations which went beyond the reference limit.

3.2 Stove performance

3.2.1 Boiling time

Figure 3 shows the comparison for the boiling time between all stoves during the cold and hot start phases of the WBT. The fastest stove to boil 2.5 L of water was S3, with an average time of 9 minutes. S1 ranked 2nd place with an average time of 16.5 minutes, followed by S2 had an average time of 17.5 minutes. The typical stove was the slowest stove to boil 2.5 L of water with an average time of 39 minutes.

Table 4 Levels of PM_i for each stove during the different WBT phases

WBT Phase	S1, µg/m ³	S2, µg/m ³	S3, µg/m ³	S4, µg/m ³
Background	3,889	5,556	2,778	3,333
Cold Start	19,298	21,296	12,963	14,444
Hot Start	28,889	32,353	25,000	19,444
Simmering	10,556	6,667	6,667	6,667
Average (from cold start to simmer)	19,581	20,105	14,877	13,519
Difference between average and background concentration	15,692	14,550	12,099	10,185

Table 5 Levels of PM_r for each stove during the different WBT phases

WBT Phase	S1, µg/m ³	S2, µg/m ³	S3, µg/m ³	S4, µg/m ³
Background	-	2,778	1,111	4,444
Cold Start	10,526	12,963	12,963	10,000
Hot Start	18,889	12,745	0	10,000
Simmering	7,778	6,111	0	1,667
Average (from cold start to simmer)	12,398	10,606	4,321	7,222
Difference between average and background concentration	-	7,829	3,210	2,778

3.2.2 Specific fuel consumption

The specific fuel consumption is the amount of charcoal used to bring a kilo of water to boiling. Figure 4 shows the comparison for the specific fuel consumption between all stoves for each WBT phases. S3, which had the fastest time to boil, had the lowest mean specific fuel consumption value of 40.5 g/L boiled. In each of the water boiling phase, S3 had the lowest specific fuel consumption. S2 had the second lowest mean specific fuel consumption value of 46.45 g/L boiled, followed by S3 with a value of 49.9 g/L boiled. S4, which was observed to be the slowest stove to boil the water, had the highest specific fuel consumption.

Figure 3 – Comparison of the time to boil for each stove

Figure 4 – Comparison of the specific fuel consumption of each stove

Figure 5 – Comparison of the thermal efficiency of each stove

3.2.3 Thermal efficiency

Thermal efficiency is one of the important parameters used to assess the performance of stoves. Figure 5 shows the comparison of the thermal efficiency between all stoves in each of the WBT phases. S2 had the highest thermal efficiency with an average value of 34%. It also had the highest thermal efficiency during the hot start and simmering

phases. S2 also performed well during the simmering test with a thermal efficiency of 40%. S3 had the second highest thermal efficiency with a mean value of 29%. S1 had the third highest thermal efficiency with an average value of 23.67%. S4 had the lowest thermal efficiency with a mean value of 11.33%. Its efficiency increased from the cold start to hot start phase, but it performed poorly during the simmer phase with a thermal efficiency of only 5%.

4 Conclusion

4.1 Stove performance

The WBT has shown that all of the improved cookstoves had less time to boil, lower specific fuel consumption and higher thermal efficiency than S4. S3 exhibited the shortest boiling time and lowest specific fuel consumption, while S2 exhibited the best thermal efficiency. Based on the results, it can be concluded that the performance of the improved cookstoves were better than S4. Using improved cookstoves thus may potentially result in reduced financial costs to families in rural areas, in terms of spending on charcoal for cooking purposes.

4.2 IAQ Assessment and evaluation

Based on the results of the IAQ assessment, it can be concluded that improving the design of the cookstove can lower the contaminants emitted. However, stove design improvement alone is not enough to lower the contaminants within standards.

4.2.1 Carbon dioxide

S3 had the lowest CO₂ concentration, followed by S2. S4 exhibited the highest CO₂ concentration. All the 8-h TWA concentration for each stove were within reference limit and may not be considered an IAQ concern in this study. CO₂ emissions may be positively correlated with boiling time and specific fuel consumption.

4.2.2 Carbon monoxide

For the CO concentrations, S2 had the lowest CO concentrations recorded and were all within the reference limit. However, the CO concentrations for the other three stoves during the cold start and hot start phases exceeded the limit. The less CO concentrations obtained for the improved stove 2 were most likely due to its high thermal efficiency.

The results may suggest that design of improved cookstoves have to focus on increasing thermal efficiency to reduce CO emissions.

4.2.3 Particulate matter

For both PM_i and PM_r, S3 and S4 were observed to have the lowest concentrations. All stoves exceeded the limit for PM_i, while interestingly; the concentration of PM_r for S4 was within the limit, outperforming all the improved stoves—which had PM_r concentrations above the limit. This suggests that improved stoves may be more efficient, but may do more harm than good as far as PM emissions is concerned.

5 Recommendations

It is recommended to pursue more walkthrough observations to obtain much more complete information about typical kitchen and stove set-ups used in rural areas. Variations of kitchen and stove set-ups may exist due to differences in cultural and geographical preferences. Much more advanced measuring equipment should be used in future studies to obtain much more precise and accurate results. Furthermore, actual IAQ sampling inside kitchens of rural households may provide real-world data, which are difficult to be provided by experiments performed inside confined laboratories.

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